

CARBOHYDRATES IN GREEN AND ROASTED COFFEE

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There has been some diversity of opinion regarding the sugars of coffee. Presence of sucrose in coffee has been reported by Spencer¹ and by Ewell². Presence of galactan, mannan and pentosans has been reported by Schultze and Maxwell³, and Hehner and Skertchley⁴. Baker⁵ found that manno-arabinose or manno-xylose formed one of the important constituents of coffee berry. However, no systematic study has been made on the changes taking place in sugars during roasting of coffee excepting the observation that sucrose is almost completely destroyed during roasting. The amount of soluble sugars extracted during brewing has also not been ascertained. The present paper describes the results obtained in a preliminary study of the total hydrolysable sugars in green and roasted coffee and their chromatographic picture (Fig. 1).

EXPERIMENTAL

Green and medium roasted coffee belonging to Arabica and Robusta varieties, grown in Coorg, were used in the present study. Green coffee was softened by soaking in water overnight in a refrigerator and then made into a fine powder in a mikropulverizer and dried in a cabinet drier. A powder passing through a 30-mesh sieve was thus obtained. No signs of fermentation were observed during soaking and subsequent treatment.

Preliminary studies were conducted to ascertain the optimum conditions for hydrolysis of the carbohydrates, both in the powder and the brew, prepared from roasted coffee. The powder (2 g.) was refluxed in boiling water with 100 c.c. of *N*-HCl and 2*N*-HCl for different periods of time ranging from 1 to 6 hours. The reducing sugars were determined after neutralisation and clarification with lead acetate by the Lane Eynon method. A 5% w/v brew was prepared by steeping for 10 minutes in boiling water and 50 c.c. of the brew was hydrolysed with *N*-HCl for varying periods of time, and the total reducing sugars determined as above,

TABLE I
Conditions for hydrolysis of carbohydrates in coffee.

	Conc. of HCl.	% Total reducing sugars as glucose after hydrolysis for					
		1 hr.	2 hrs.	3 hrs.	4 hrs.	5 hrs.	6 hrs.
Medium roasted coffee powder (Pl. A.)	1 N	21.6	24.8	27.4	27.8	28.8	26.6
	2	26.2	27.2	27.8	28.8	27.7	26.0
5% (w/v, brew)	1	0.112 (2.24)*	0.16 (3.20)	0.188 (3.76)	0.190 (3.80)	0.195 (3.90)	0.170 (3.40)

*Figures in parantheses give values of sugars in brew as per cent of powder.

Table I shows that the optimum conditions of hydrolysis are refluxing with *N*-HCl for 5 hours. These conditions were followed for determining the total sugars in green and roasted coffee. The free reducing sugars and total reducing sugars after inversion with *N*-HCl at 67° for 9 minutes were determined separately in the extract obtained by steeping coffee with boiling water for 10 minutes. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II
Total reducing sugars in green and roasted coffee.

Coffee.	Reducing sugars (green coffee).		Reducing sugars (moisture-free basis)			
	Before inversion.	After inversion.	Green coffee.	Roasted coffee.		
				Light.	Medium.	Dark.
Arabica Plantation	Trace	4.56%	29.7%	27.8%	25.1%	16.4%
Robusta Cherry	..	3.80	31.1	...	29.0	...

Chromatographic studies.—Both ascending and descending techniques were used with *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 5) and *n*-butanol-alcohol-water (4 : 1 : 5). For spotting sugars, benzidine reagent (0.5 g. benzidine + 10 c.c. glacial acetic acid + 10 c.c. 40% w/v trichloroacetic acid + 80 c.c. alcohol) was sprayed and the chromatogram was kept in the hot air-oven till spots developed. Development time varied from 18 to 36 hours. Whatman No. 1 filter paper (57 cm. × 24 cm.) was used for the chromatograms.

The coffee powder (2 g.) was extracted by boiling with 10 c.c. water for 5 minutes and filtered. After concentration to 5 c.c. on a water-bath, the solution, before and after inversion, was spotted on the filter paper. Hydrolysis of the powder was carried out for 5 hours with *N*-HCl as stated earlier and the hydrolysate was also spotted. The polysaccharides in the coffee extract were precipitated with 4 volumes of alcohol and hydrolysed for chromatographic examination. The sugar spots were identified both by running known sugars and by mixed chromatograms. Table III (Fig. 1) describes the qualitative make-up of the sugars in coffee.

TABLE III

Chromatographic picture of sugars in coffee.

	Suc-rose.	Glucose.	Fructose.	Galactose.	Mannose.	Arabinose.
1 Green coffee extract (Plantation A)	+	Trace	—	—	—	—
2 Roasted coffee extract	Trace	—	—	—	—	—
3 Green coffee extract, Inverted (67°)	—	+	+	—	—	—
4 Roasted coffee extract, Inverted (67°)	—	Trace	Trace	—	—	—
5 Green coffee extract, hydrolysed (98°)	—	—	—	+	+	+
6 Roasted coffee extract, hydrolysed (98°)	—	—	—	+	+	+
7 Robusta cherry green, hydrolysed (98°)	—	—	—	+	+	+
8 Robusta cherry roasted, hydrolysed (98°)	—	—	—	+	+	+

Chromatograms of hydrolysates from powder were similar to those from the corresponding extracts

FIG. 1

A. Arabinose. F. Fructose. GL. Glucose. GA. Galactose. M. Mannose. S. Sucrose.
 1. Known sugars. 2. Green coffee extract. 3. Roasted coffee extract. 4. Green coffee extract inverted.
 I. Known sugars. II. Known sugars. III. Green coffee hydrolysed (98°). IV. Roasted coffee hydrolysed (98°). V-VI. Known sugars.

DISCUSSION

The amount of reducing sugars obtainable from coffee after hydrolysis is about 30% of which about 4% is extracted into the decoction under normal conditions of brewing. There does not seem to be much difference in reducing sugars between the two varieties, namely, *C. arabica* and *C. robusta*. Under normal hydrolytic conditions for sucrose, the polysaccharides in coffee

are not hydrolysed. Longer hydrolysis at higher temperature was necessary and treatment for 5 hours with *N*-HCl at 98° was found satisfactory.

Chromatographic studies have shown the presence of sucrose and trace of glucose in green coffee. Roasted coffee contained very little or traces of the two sugars. In the hydrolysate from the polysaccharides, galactose, arabinose and mannose were detected both from green and roasted coffee. From the intensity of spots, it was observed that arabinose content was less than that of mannose and galactose. Roasting resulted in the loss of reducing sugars and dark roast contained nearly half of that present in green coffee.

With benzidine reagent in cold, a yellow spot was noticed very near the solvent front. Similar spots have also been observed by us in chicory and coffee husk. The identity of this has not been established yet, but it appears to be a degradation product formed during hydrolysis.

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S U M M A R Y

The total reducing sugars in coffee (on hydrolysis) amount to 30% out of which only 4% is extracted in the brew. Chromatographic studies have confirmed the presence in coffee of glucose, fructose, sucrose, arabinose, galactose and mannose.

R E F E R E N C E S

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